

A Study on Impact of Organizational Support on Employee Work-Life Balance and Job Satisfaction Among School Teachers in Cuddalore District

1. M. Vennila
Ph.D. Research Scholar
Department of Commerce
Annamalai University

2. Dr. M. Somasundaram
Professor of Commerce
Annamalai University

Received: May 16, 2025

Accepted: Jun 14, 2025

Published: Jun 16, 2025

Abstract

In today's economic environment, women working in private schools strive to balance their professional and personal lives while contributing effectively to their institutions. As educators, they are expected to give their best to their students and the school, while also fulfilling their responsibilities at home. Achieving this balance requires not only individual effort but also strong support from both the workplace and family. To study this, the researchers conducted a study on the work-life balance (WLB) and job satisfaction of women working in private schools, with a focus on the impact of organizational support. The study gathered data from 239 respondents through questionnaires and direct interviews. Using percentage analysis, correlation, and the Chi-Square test, the research findings indicated that organizational support significantly influences the work-life balance and job satisfaction of female educators. A supportive work environment fosters loyalty, enhances job satisfaction, and contributes to a positive and balanced professional and personal life.

Keywords: Employee, Job Satisfaction, Work Life, Balance, Family, Organisation.

Introduction

Women of today is working in all the organisation in India. As of the statistics of 2023, the female labour force participation has improved a lot from 4.2% to 37.0% (According to the

Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS) 2022-23 released by the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation)¹.

Source: Periodic Labour Force Survey 2022-23.

Women in India are working for many reasons such as for livelihood, improving the standard of living, additional income of the family, asset creation, wealth creation, marriage, children education, supporting family, medical expenses, and high life style. The education of the women has made them independent in all aspects. They work in different organisations, and the greater they work is the educational sector. Though they work in schools and colleges, they have to balance themselves in work and the family. They have to balance the family, children, household activities, preparation for the next day classes, organising the house, managing the children's studies etc. When coming to job, if the organisation supports the women, they would be able to balance their work Life and that increases the job satisfaction of the women. The topic has been taken for study to understand the Impact of Organizational Support on Employee Work-Life Balance and Job Satisfaction.

Review of literature

Veenalatha. K, (2019), study on "A study on work life balance of the employees in the field of education" the researcher concluded that Work-life balance is a very important issue in the Human Resource Management field and it has a vital impact on the productivity and growth of both the organization and the employee. Many factors act as supporting elements for employees to achieve balance between work and personal life. While certain elements like employees participation in framing the policies and taking key decisions, effective communication of organizations policies can be strengthened to make work and personal life of employees highly balanced.

¹Ministry of Women and Child Development, Posted On: 13 OCT 2023 12:11PM by PIB Delhi. DOI: [Press Release: Press Information Bureau](#)

Prachita Patil, Yogesh Deshpande (2021), understanding perception of women entrepreneurs towards employees with reference to quality of work life balance (QWLB), in their study they concluded the work life scale between start-ups and established women entrepreneur and comparing their type of firm as a single proprietorship, working with spouse and with partners. Quality of work life balance issues faced by Indian Women Entrepreneurs.

Kajtazi K June (2021), women entrepreneurs and the challenge of work life balance : Evidence from Kosovo, Author indicated that the majority of female entrepreneurs' face difficulties on work – life balancing, but to overcome this challenge, they engage their family members on business activities and also, women who are married, especially those with than one child have more difficulties on this aspect than those unmarried.

Statement of problem

Women are playing major role in home, in their work place also they have more responsibility in all sector. In teaching field especially in schools are depending women teachers. They are understand their role and take care of the children, male are take some other responsibility in schools. Their part in the student's development are significant and unavoidable one. They need favourable working environment to do their job more effective, this study needs to conduct to understand the level of favourable work place environment.

Objectives of the problem

The following are the objectives of the study.

1. To present the socio economic factors of the sample respondents.
2. To find the variables and analysis the variables of level of agreement about the factors affecting the balance of personal and work life.
3. To offer suggestions to the management and employees.

Sampling Design

The researcher conducted the present study in Cuddalore district, there are many private schools are functioning in this District. The researcher adopted convenient sampling method for this study for data collection. Structured questionnaire was prepared and distributed to the school teachers, 250 questionnaires were distributed and collected back only 239, all the 239 questionnaires were used for this study.

Tools and techniques

The researcher used percentage analysis and chi square test in this paper, the percentage analysis used to presents the socio economic factors of the respondents. Likert five point scale used to find the level of agreement about the factors affecting the balance of personal and work life. Chi square test used to find the factors which influence the level of agreement about the factors affecting the balance of personal and work life and test the hypothesis.

Hypothesis

The socio economic factors not significantly influence the level of agreement about the factors affecting the balance of personal and work life of the respondents.

Analysis and interpretation

Table 1 : Age group of the respondents

Sl. No.	Age group	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Up to 30 years	35	14.64
2	30 to 40 years	86	35.98
3	41 to 50 years	63	26.37
4	Above 50 years	55	23.01
	Total	239	100

Source : Primary data

The above table presents the age group of the respondents, out of two hundred and thirty nine sample respondents, thirty five (14.64%) respondents are up to 30 years old. Eighty six (35.98%) respondents are between 30 years and 40 years old. Sixty three (26.37%) respondents are between 41 years and 50 years old and remaining fifty five (23.01%) respondents are above 50 years old. Majority (35.98%) of the respondents are 30 years to 40 years.

Table 2 : Educational qualification of the respondents

Sl. No.	Educational Qualification	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Under Graduate	25	10.46
2	Post Graduate	46	19.25
3	B.Ed.	105	43.93
4	M.Ed.	63	26.36
	Total	239	100

Source : Primary data

The above table presents the educational qualification of the respondents, out of two hundred and thirty nine sample respondents, twenty five (10.46%) respondents are under graduate. Forty six (19.25%) respondents are did post graduate. One hundred and five (43.92%) respondents did B.Ed. and remaining sixty-three (26.36%) respondents are doing M.Ed. Majority (43.93%) of the respondents are did B.Ed.

Table 3 : Level of employment of the respondents

Sl. No.	Level of employment	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Primary level teacher	74	30.96
2	Secondary level teacher	113	47.28
3	Senior Secondary level teacher	52	21.76
	Total	239	100

Source : Primary data

The above table shows the level of employment of the respondents, out of two hundred and thirty nine sample respondents, seventy four (30.96%) respondents are primary level teachers. One hundred and thirteen (47.28%) respondents are secondary level teachers and remaining fifty two (21.76%) respondents are senior secondary level teachers. Majority (47.28%) of the respondents are secondary level teachers.

Table 4 : Teaching Experience of the respondents

Sl. No.	Teaching Experience	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 10 years	64	26.78
2	11 years to 15 years	123	51.46
3	Above 15 years	52	21.76
	Total	239	100

Source : Primary data

The above table presents the experience in the field of teaching, out of two hundred and thirty nine sample respondents, sixty four (26.78%) respondents are less than 10 years of experience. One hundred and twenty three (51.46%) respondents are 11 to 15 years of teaching experience and remaining fifty two (21.76%) respondents are above 15 years of teaching experience. Majority (54.46%) of the respondents are between 11 years and 15 years of teaching experience.

Table 5 : Family type of the respondents

Sl. No.	Family type	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Nuclear	147	61.51
2	Joint	92	38.49
	Total	239	100

Source : Primary data

The above table shows the family type of the sampler respondents, out of two hundred and thirty nine sample respondents, one hundred and forty seven (61.51%) respondents are nuclear family respondents and remaining ninety two (38.49%) respondents are joint family respondents. Majority (61.51%) of the respondents are nuclear family respondents.

Table 6 : Number of Family members of the respondents

Sl. No.	Number of Family members	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	3 members	138	57.74
2	4 to 5 members	57	23.85
3	Above 5 members	44	18.41
	Total	239	100

Source : Primary data

The above table shows the number of family members of the respondents, out of two hundred and thirty nine respondents, one hundred and thirty eight (57.74%) respondents' family members are 3. Fifty seven (23.85%) respondents' family members are 4 to 5 members and remaining forty four (18.41%) respondent's family members are above 5. Majority (57.74%) of the respondents' number of family members are 3.

Table 7 : Monthly family income

Sl. No.	Monthly family income	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Less than Rs. 30,000 per month	102	42.68
2	Rs. 30,001 to Rs. 60,000 per month	71	29.71
3	Above Rs. 60,000 per month	66	27.61
	Total	239	100

Source : Primary data

The above table shows the monthly family income of the respondents, out of two hundred and thirty nine sample respondents, one hundred and two (42.68%) respondent's monthly family income is less than Rs. 30,000. Seventy one (29.71%) respondent's monthly family income is between Rs. 30,001 and Rs. 60,000 and remaining sixty six (27.61%) respondent's monthly family income is above Rs. 60,000 per month. Majority (42.68%) of the respondent's monthly family income is less than Rs. 30,000.

Level of Job Satisfaction

Table 8: Level of Job Satisfaction

Sl. No.	Level of Job Satisfaction	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Highly Satisfied	21	8.79
2	Satisfied	31	12.97
3	Neutral	82	34.31
4	Dissatisfied	57	23.85
5	Highly dissatisfied	48	20.08
	Total	239	100

Source : Computed data

The above table shows the level of job satisfaction, out of two hundred and thirty nine sample respondents, twenty one (8.79%) respondents are high satisfied about their job satisfaction. Thirty one (12.97%) respondents are satisfied about their job satisfaction. Eighty one (34.31%) respondents are neutral about their job satisfaction. Fifty seven (23.85%) respondents are dissatisfied about their job satisfaction and remaining forty eight (20.08%) respondents are highly satisfied about their job satisfaction. Majority (34.31%) of the respondents are neutral about their job satisfaction.

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Chi Square test

The researcher have taken fourteen variables to find the level of organizational support. Used five-point Likert scale to find the level of organizational support. Mean and standard deviation calculated to find the number of respondents being in the level, i.e., low, medium and high. The following table shows the level of organizational support.

Table 9: Level of Impact of Organizational Support

Sl. No.	Level of impact of Organizational support	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Low	91	38.08
2	Medium	113	47.28
3	High	35	14.64
	Total	239	100
Mean : 48.783, SD : 2.730, Minimum : 23, Maximum : 53			

Source : Computed data

The above table shows the level of favourable work place environment, out of one hundred and seventy three respondents, seventy seven (44.51%) respondents felt low level of unfavourable work place environment, fifty eight (33.52%) respondents felt medium level of unfavourable work place environment and remaining thirty eight (21.97%) respondents felt high level of unfavourable work place environment. Majority (33.52%) of the respondents are felt medium level of unfavourable work place environment. It conclude that more number of respondents felt unfavourable work place environment.

Table 10: Chi Square test - Level of Job Satisfaction

Sl. No.	Variables	Chi Square value	DF	P – Value	Result
1	Age group	22.871	4	0.001	Significant
2	Educational Qualification	18.489	4	0.001	Significant
3	Level of employment	11.392	4	0.001	Significant
4	Teaching Experience	31.478	4	0.001	Significant
5	Family type	11.820	2	0.001	Significant
6	Number of Family members	14.651	4	0.001	Significant
7	Monthly family income	13.904	4	0.001	Significant

Source : Computed data

Hypothesis

The socio economic factors not significantly influence the level of job satisfaction of the respondents.

The above table shows the chi square output of the sample respondents, age group (0.001), educational qualification (0.001), level of employment (0.001), teaching experience (0.001), family type (0.001), number of family members (0.001) and monthly family income (0.001) are significantly influence the level of job satisfaction, hence the null hypothesis has been rejected at 5% significant level. All the above said variables are significantly influence the job satisfaction. If the respondents age increase they may feel more job satisfaction, like that the above said variable changes influence the job satisfaction.

Table 11: Correlation : Impact of organizational support and Job Satisfaction

		Impact of Organizational Support	Job Satisfaction
Impact of Organizational support	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	239	
Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	0.944**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	239	239

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The above table shows the relationship between organizational support and job satisfaction. There is positive and significant relationship between organizational support and job satisfaction at 1% significant level. It shows that organizational support is more important to the employees, employees are working for salary the same time their effort helps for the organizational development. So, the management should understand this and support the staff which will help for the organization development.

Findings of the study

The following are the findings of the study

1. Majority (35.98%) of the respondents are 30 years to 40 years.
2. Majority (43.93%) of the respondents have graduated B.Ed.
3. Majority (47.28%) of the respondents are secondary level teachers.
4. Majority (54.46%) of the respondents are between 11 years and 15 years of teaching experience.
5. Majority (61.51%) of the respondents are nuclear family respondents.
6. Majority (57.74%) of the respondents' number of family members are 3.
7. Majority (42.68%) of the respondent's monthly family income is less than Rs. 30,000.

8. Majority (34.31%) of the respondents are neutral about their job satisfaction.

It concludes that a greater number of respondents felt unfavourable work place environment and if the respondents age increase, they may feel more job satisfaction, like that the above said variable changes influence the job satisfaction. So, the management should understand this and support the staff which will help for the organization development.

Suggestions for the study

The following are some of the suggestions for the organization and the employees working in the organisation:

1. The organisation having a positive support towards the employees would reduce stress, that increases the work life satisfaction among the employees.
2. An adjustable time for starting and ending to accommodate personal commitments might improve the feel of belongingness towards the management.
3. The long-term employees could be allowed to take longer days of leave for personal development and rest for better physical health as well as mental health.
4. The organisation should provide access to gym involvements, yoga classes, and wellness for the benefits of the employees such as sessions for mental fitness, meditation, and work-life integration tactics.
5. Organisation might provide lactating mothers with peaceful spaces for nursing children.
6. Training should be given to the managers to identify and talk about the employees' work-life needs, and encourage employees to speak out their sorrows without the fear of judgment.
7. The employees should be rewarded for their contributions to maintain self-confidence.
8. Automated technologies have to be used to minimize manual and repetitive works.
9. The works should be given in rotation to make the employees stay supportive to each other.
10. The management must understand that a well satisfied worker will be the best working employee in any organisation.

Conclusion

The above study has highlighted the organisational efforts and the employee WLB and the job satisfaction of the women employees working in private school in Cuddalore district. The women working in schools and in other organisations have to adjust and balance their work life and their family life. This could be done with the supporting hands from the organisation to the employees. The management addressing the issues of the women and supporting in the form of adjustable working hours, sanction of long leaves for health and fitness, maternity and paid leaves might give a feel of belongingness towards the organisation they work with. Monetary as well as non-monetary benefits would definitely encourage the employees to work with heart that improves the efficiency of an organisation. A satisfied employee grows the organisation to a new-heights. Understanding the need of the employees, providing proper recognition and rewards will make any organisation to grow and prosper in the place of establishment, which in turn gives a goodwill for the organisation.

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